

The Benefits and Challenges of Urban Forestry in Ghana

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The research is financed by Jiangsu University School of finance and Economics. (008651188780011)

Abstract

This present study aims to evaluate urban forestry development, assess the impact of population growth on urban forestry development, and propose some recommendations for sustainable development of Ghana's urban cities. The methods used to investigate the challenges and benefits of urban forestry in Ghana are: (i) information gathered on spot assessment from relevant stakeholders, (ii) data gathered from secondary sources, (iii) inventory of peri-urban and urban facilities in Kumasi and Accra, and (iv) structured questionnaire distributed to personnel at the forestry commission to ascertain the challenges and benefits of urban forestry. Urban forestry in Ghana suffers inadequate strategic information and coordinated action for its implementation. In essence, urban forestry development requires enhanced information dissemination and sharing by establishing a network of people and a network of knowledge. Most appropriately, a well managed urban forestry should have essential penurious potential and perform environmental functions. The study has outlined that the provision of essential products and services as potentials of urban forestry can be maintained through an appropriately integrated management approach. In achieving sustainable urban forestry practice, all stakeholders should establish, plan, protect, and maintain urban forests. Education and awareness campaigns should be intensified concerning urban forestry

Keywords: Urban forestry; Sustainable urban cities; urbanization; benefits and challenges of the urban forestry in Ghana

Introduction

For the past five decades, West Africa's population growth has significantly quadrupled. In 1950, the sub-region population was nearly 71 million, which increased to 234.7 million in 2000 and subsequently increased to 267.8 million in 2005. Moreover, in 2010, the population stood at 307 million, with a projected increase to 401.8 million in 2020 (World Population Prospects, 2019). Specifically, every country in the sub-region is encountered with higher urban settlement more than rural settlement. Although most countries in the sub-region have experienced great development and nurtured great empires for religious and commercial purposes, urbanization remains a phenomenon in West Africa (Chandler, 1994; Fuwape & Onyekwelu, 2010). The trend in urbanization in West Africa can be attributed to the development of administration, control, and export of exploited resources through colonization in the sub-region.

Nonetheless, Africa's urbanization rate to other countries is comparatively diverse (Tathey, 2005; Palen, 1997; Okpala, 1987; Butler & Crooke, 1973). In the demographical context, migration in America and Europe results from the urban pull effect, which is the primary factor of urbanization (Dutt & Parai, 1994). Unlike Africa, the primary factor of urbanization is the rural push effect due to a fast urbanization rate compared to the developed countries, which is quite gradual (Tathey, 2005). According to the United Nations (2020), Ghana's current population stands at 31.07 million, estimated to reach 78.1 million in 2099. In 1960, Ghana's population was about 6.6 million, which increased to 11.1 million in 1980 and subsequently to about 19.3 million in 2000. The growth rate in Ghana's population is aligned to the country's efforts to minimize birth mortalities and high fertility of 3.89 births per woman. Admittedly, the growth rate has reduced from 2.95% in 1985 to 2.15% but remains high. The urbanization of Ghana for 2000-2005 was 4.06%, which decreased to 3.97% for 2005-2010, perhaps, it is expected to decrease to 3.34% for 2015-2020, but it is quite alarming. The land size of the country is about 227,540 km² with a population density of 137/km². Scores of experts have criticized population growth, claiming that it poses a threat to socio-economic development. It causes a tremendous increase in water, food, sanitation, employment, and

education needs. Moreover, they suggest that family planning and reducing the number of births or spacing out births could be the antidote to this canker.

Figure 1 Ghana's Population density map

Ghana's largest region by population size, Greater Accra, occupies only 185 km² of land and accounts for 4 million. Accra, the urban city, which is the capital city, occupies about 2.27 million inhabitants, making the city heavily population and the 11th largest metro area in Africa (United Nations, 2019). However, the population density of the capital city could be ranging from 1,200 to 7,000 per km². The capital city has witnessed an influx of rural migrants and which led to heavy congestion. Since 1877, the city has experienced massive transformation into one of Africa's largest cities from a once-sleepy coastal fishing village during the British colonial administration.

The major challenges facing the central government, metropolitan, and municipal authorities are the unavailability of infrastructures and essential public goods to meet the growing population demand. Most significantly, in peri-urban and urban areas in Ghana, authorities' control of settlement planning is very lousy. Even though some cities have orchestrated and master plans to mitigate and govern the pressures from population growth, the implementation of such plans is lax. The population growth in Ghana's urban cities throws light on more challenges such as scarce natural resources, pressure on lands, inadequate infrastructures, and environmental pollution. To be specific, deteriorating air quality, shortage of food and land, shortage in wood and energy provision for construction, increased noise, a higher level of air temperatures, psychological stress, etc.

One of the leading solutions to urbanization is urban forestry (Fuwape & Onyekwelu, 2010) due to its capability of addressing the multifaceted headaches surrounding urbanization. In Ghana, trees' planting has

an essential and pertinent issue of human settlements, but urban dwellers did not consider the maximum value of trees planting (Fuwape & Onyekwelu, 2010). Conventionally, Ghanaians happen to plant trees that bear nuts, fruits, seeds, fuelwood, leaves, and raw materials for handicrafts around their houses to serve as shades and windbreaks. Mostly, trees are planted along stream banks, rivers, village roads, religious and cultural centers. Usually, the management and planting of trees in Ghana are basically for social, nutritional, spiritual, and cultural values other than aesthetic reasons. The situation of urbanization in Ghana, coupled with urban population growth, has revealed the need for urban forestry practices. Also, it has outlined a new opportunity and challenge.

Nonetheless, urban forestry does not only serve as essential goods and services but also serve as amenity oriented services. Greening the urban spaces with trees serve as a pivotal role for sustainable cities and healthy living. Planting trees in urban cities acts as natural filters by keeping the city cool, absorbing noises, conserving biodiversity, improving microclimates, protecting and improving the water bodies, soil, wildlife, and vegetation quality. The aesthetic charm of cities from planting trees contributes significantly to the psychological health of the people living in the city. According to Jiang (2003), an urban forestry management strategy serves as a vital function to improve and enhance urban inhabitants' living conditions and working environments. The urban forestry concept encompasses the design, planning, establishment, and management of trees within urban cities. However, it is crucial to focus on the influences of rapid urbanization and population growth on urban forest development (Konijnendijk et al., 2006; Forrest and Konijnendijk 2005). This present study aims to evaluate urban forestry development, assess the impact of population growth on urban forestry development, and propose some recommendations for sustainable development of Ghana's urban cities.

Materials and methods

The methods used to investigate the challenges and benefits of urban forestry in Ghana are: (i) information gathered on spot assessment from relevant stakeholders, (ii) data gathered from secondary sources, (iii) inventory of peri-urban and urban facilities in Kumasi and Accra, and (iv) structured questionnaire distributed to personnel at the forestry commission to ascertain the challenges and benefits of urban forestry. Moreover, the impact of urbanization and population growth on urban forestry was also assessed. The secondary data was collected from the United Nations data repository; thus, World Population Prospects (2019) and World Urbanization Prospects (2018).

Findings discussion

The spatial dimension is the most obvious in the process of urbanization. Moreover, urban areas' dynamics when human and city agglomerations grow could be seen as either a spatial expansion or densification of the core where urban demarcation expands (Akerlund et al., 2006; UN Habitat, 2004). In the process of densification, buildings already existing could either be newly built or extended. However, densification simply means the volume of built-up structure and population density (persons living per km²). Urban sprawl means expanding urban fringe, which happens on urban green resources such as woodlots, forests, orchards, or agricultural lands.

Most prime cities in Ghana tend to grow through urban sprawl and densification. This development indicates an increasing population density and city expansion actively. Nonetheless, some cities are vividly merging with neighboring cities. Consequently, this condition has occasioned by the de-afforestation, destruction of urban parks and agricultural lands, orchards, and gardens due to the construction of industries and houses. Primarily, the strategies for spatial development planning of Ghana have a great weakness in recent times, which can be attributed to inconsistent land reforms, spontaneous land privatization, inadequate information on ownership, and land-use.

Moreover, incomprehensive and imperfect legislative frameworks are characterized by the strategies for regulating spatial development planning. In retrospect, weak coordination of activities and issues of land regulations, and lack of cooperation among government agencies and authorities are also part of the strategical lapses. Due to the large rural population and higher growth rate in urbanization in Ghana, many shanty and slums exist in the urban cities. The country's economic condition prevails, an unprecedented

decline in living standards, a rise in inequality, and many households residing in slums (UN Habitat, 2004; Van der Jagt & Lawrence, 2019).

In Ghana, the main kinds of urban forestry are (i) designated parks, roadside plantations, and street trees, (ii) semi-private area like green space in industrial and residential areas, (iii) public green spaces like green parks, recreational gardens, and botanical gardens, (iv) forests close to urban areas, and rangeland, (v) private and public tree plantations on green belts, vacant lots, peri-urban tree plantations, and woodlands, (vi) trees planted for watersheds and windbreak, purposefully for environmental protection, and (vii) natural forest such as national parks, nature reserves, and forests for eco-tourism. These forests' physiognomy, floristic features, socio-economic importance, and characteristics vary regarding their ecological zones where they are situated. There are six vegetational or ecological zones in Ghana; thus, Guinea savannah, Sudan Savannah, Rain forest zone, coastal savannah, deciduous forest zone, and forest/savannah transitional zone (Adjei-Nsiah, 2013). (see figure 2).

Figure 2 Ecological/vegetational zones in Ghana

In particular, the ecological factors characterized by these vegetational zones significantly impact the livelihoods of the people and urban forestry landscape (Fuwape et al., 2006). The purpose of tree planting in Ghana's urban cities is useful for environmental protection, landscape enhancement, provision of non-timber and timber forest products, and others. Their benefits vary regarding the kind of ecological zone situated, and each ecological zone has its species of trees that can be planted. Figure 3 below presents the ecological zones and their species of trees.

Figure 3 Species of trees in various ecological zones

Gonzalez (2001) suggested that to restore the human carrying capacity, regeneration of peri-urban forest should be done with indigenous species of trees. The socio-economic and ecological factors indicate indigenous species' preference more than the exotic species due to the exotic species' poor survival nature. In essence, trees serve as a natural habitat for wildlife and birds. Moreover, communities and small businesses conduct their businesses and other meetings under trees because of their shade. Also, some religious bodies converge under trees for their religious activities in most urban cities in Ghana.

Benefits of urban forestry

In Ghana, urban forestry resources play a critical role in providing goods and services to improve citizens' lives, enhance their wellbeing, and help in poverty alleviation. Numerous stakeholders benefit from urban forestry in diverse ways through improved legislation and policies, strategic management and planning, financial mechanisms, urban forestry practice, key stakeholders and actors capacity building and education, ownership, and access (Akerlund et al., 2006). Urban forestry in Ghana provides trees for use as wood for non-timber forest products (nuts and fruits, mushrooms, medical herbs, vegetables, rattan, etc.) and construction purposes. The practice of urban forestry has massively contributed to the progress in food security and the creation of medicinal parks or multipurpose parks. Agroforestry garden constitutes the dominant urban forestry practice in Ghana. However, most new urban settlements and urban fringes have trees in the form of fruit-bearing plantations. Also, in semi-arid and arid areas, planting of windbreak trees, are urban forestry practice is very common and is mostly planted for the protection of houses and simultaneously to improve land productivity.

Numerous households in the urban cities in Ghana are heavily dependent on firewood or fuelwood for cooking purposes. Most of them spend a significant proportion of their income on woodfuel, predominantly the urban poor population (Kuchelmeister, 2001). In urban cities, inequality still exists between the urban rich and poor regarding the use of woodfuel compared to safe and sustainable alternatives. Charcoal as an

inexpensive woodfuel is widely used by the urban poor population, derived from trees planted in the urban forests. Urban forestry provides trees such as timber for construction and building purposes as quite several urban dwellers live in shanties, fringes, and slums built with woods obtained from timber from peri-urban plantations. According to Webb (1999), the planting of street trees as systematic planting for timber production is extensively practiced in Malaysia and China. This practice is not common in West African countries and, to be precise, Ghana due to tenure insecurity, ignorance, and lack of technical know-how.

Other intangible benefits that urban forestry provides is an environmental impact. Due to congestion in urban cities like Accra and Kumasi, environmental pollution is one of the congestion effects; hence the industrial pollutions, bush burning, and automobile exhaust contribute to the environmental pollution in the urban cities. There is grave concern about global warming, which evolved the diffusion of knowledge concerning the functionality of urban trees planting for air quality and microclimates improvement. Primarily, the improvement of air quality and microclimates to reduce global warming provide settings for interception of particles, physical exercise, and reduce air pollution (Konijnendijk et al., 2004; Harris et al., 1999; McPherson & Simpson, 1999; Van der Jagt & Lawrence, 2019). Urban forestry positively impacts the physical wellbeing of urban residents. In Accra and Kumasi, tree plantations are often used for spiritual and cultural values, which significantly impact their mental health. On the other hand, trees serve as high temperature absorber. Besides, urban forests serve as a safeguard for water supply systems, stormwater management systems, and wastewater treatment systems, usually in arid, peri-urban, and semi-arid zones in the urban cities.

Urban forestry serves as car parking lots for public and private buildings where trees are planted to provide a spreading crown. These cars are protected from the scorching sun by the trees. Also, it provides shelter for domestic animals and humans for its reduction in ultraviolet radiation from the scorching sun (Konijnendijk et al., 2004; Van der Jagt & Lawrence, 2019). More importantly, urban forestry provides students with a shelter to relax and play during their break times and provide shade for market traders in open markets in the urban areas. Planting trees in urban areas moderates harsh urban climates and protects soils by reducing wind speeds, cooling the air, and shading. For micro-climate, the trees in urban cities absorb carbon dioxide and moderate diurnal range of air temperature. It also replenishes oxygen in the air and reduces other gaseous pollutants (Konijnendijk et al., 2004). In the Sudan and Sahel savannah zones, trees planted serves as windbreak due to the strong wind effects that could affect buildings and other facilities. Over there, the trees suppress the wind speed to protect the buildings and structures from destruction (Fuwape, 2005). Trees like avenue trees beautify the urban cities and provide aesthetic green features for monotones connected to concrete buildings.

Peri-urban agroforests, gardens and parks, protected zones, and botanical gardens as urban forestry practices play an essential role in nature conservation. The embedment of tree planting in urban landscape projects ensures biodiversity and biological conservation. Greenways and greenbelts also reconnect the urban cities and their environs through biological corridors. Perhaps, urban green areas by the level of its biodiversity are often high, bringing nature close to the people. Some cities like Rio de Janeiro, Singapore, and Kuala Lumpur are known for their tropical rainforest tactically situated (Konijnendijk *et al.*, 2004; Webb, 1999; Lakany, 1999; Chin & Corlett, 1986; Van der Jagt & Lawrence, 2019). Urban forestry serves as recreational facilities through its botanical gardens and green parks, which are patronized by urban dwellers and other people for funfairs and picnics. The high rate of urbanization and peri-urban population growth threatens the benefits and imposes some urban forest development challenges on top of these benefits.

Challenges of urban forestry

Enormous challenges are characterized by rapid urbanization in Ghana. The largest cities, such as Accra and Kumasi, are more than tripled in population and size for the past five decades. The pressing issue has led to the destruction of forest and green spaces; perhaps, this is expected to persist for the coming decades. One of the main challenges is rural-urban migration to the megacities, and this had led to poverty, hunger, inadequate and improper shelter, unemployment, social exclusion, pollution of the atmosphere, water, and soil, etc. urban forestry is crippled with a fundamental challenge, thus maintaining and developing a

sustainable urban forest that could meet the standard of personal and multiple societal needs. The management of urban forest requires the planting, maintaining, and developing multiple trees or products and services that could be valuable to society and other stakeholders. Therefore, multipurpose tree species are needed in urban forestry in Ghana. The structure of urban forestry has a key impact on determining the best mix and mix of outputs required on trade-offs between the outputs, values, and costs. The outputs of urban forestry are classified as competitive or complementary. Urban forestry output is complementary when an increase in the other complements an increase in output (Van der Jagt & Lawrence, 2019).

In contrast, it is termed as competitive when an increase in output leads to a reduction in the other. The destruction of tree gardens, peri-urban plantations, and recreational parks for housing projects due to rapid urbanization is an immediate challenge to urban forestry. Many urban dwellers do not have the muscle to rent houses or pay for mortgages through rural-urban migration, hence embark on their housing projects. Since they cannot afford well-allocated housing areas, they sometimes build on watersheds, which causes flooding and water flow. Others also put up slums, which cause environmental hazards. The destruction of land for infrastructural development or projects is another consequence of rapid urbanization on the peri-urban and urban forest. Pressures on governments and land speculators have led to the destruction of many social amenities through rapid urbanization. The poor urban dwellers have resorted to cutting down trees in the botanical gardens and the trees for cooking because they cannot afford conventional cooking equipment.

That notwithstanding, most gardens and recreational parks have converted into garbage collection sites in Accra and Kumasi. Funding for urban forestry is one of the major challenges as little funds are usually allocated to develop urban forestry in Ghana. However, funds are mostly allocated to provide healthcare and education rather than urban forestry establishment and management. Some of the challenges that urban forestry in Ghana faces are: (i) inadequate appreciation of the economic value of urban forestry; (ii) little research, technological transfer, and information exchange; (iii) ineffective land-use policies; (iv) insufficient private and government participation; (v) integration of forestry into urban planning and development; (vi) sustainable funding for urban forestry; and (vii) technical and ecological constraints.

Conclusion

To cope with rapid urbanization and urban forestry challenges, governments and policymakers should ensure a review of forest policies to curtail urban forestry's current trend to ensure sustainable urban cities. The policies used in the country are influenced by colonial practices that monopolized urban forestry practice by the government by considering the participation of other stakeholders. It creates indifference of the people to destroy the forest and urban forest development (Amanor, 2003). To achieve a sustainable urban forestry practice, an integrated participatory forestry approach should be instituted to involve all stakeholders in designing, planning, maintaining, and establishing the forest. However, the essential thing is to decipher the major needs and issues facing people, such as poverty alleviation, environmental needs, and livelihoods.

Urban forestry in Ghana suffers inadequate strategic information and coordinated action for its implementation (FAO, 2002). In essence, urban forestry development requires enhanced information dissemination and sharing by establishing a network for the people and knowledge network (Konijnendijk et al., 2004). Most appropriately, a well managed urban forestry should have essential penurious potential and perform environmental functions. Education must be provided to people to understand the importance of urban forestry in every development strategy. Also, community participation in the management and maintenance of avenue trees, peri-urban plantations, and botanical gardens is highly important to curtail the incidences of encroachments and deforestation (Hosek, 2014). A collaboration of stakeholders ought to be ensured because their perception could influence their decision in preserving and conserving the urban forests. Therefore, the private sector, community leaders and members, and government authorities should form part of the decision-making body to provide effective urban forestry practice. It will ensure sustainable environmental practices of the natural environment, which has economic and social benefits. Also, urban forestry has health implications on the environment (Van der Jagt & Lawrence, 2019).

The rapid urbanization and high population growth rate negatively impact urban forestry and perhaps have responsibility for the vicious cycle of environmental destruction in Ghana's urban areas. The study has outlined that the provision of essential products and services as potentials of urban forestry can be maintained through an appropriately integrated management approach. To achieve a sustainable urban forestry practice, all stakeholders should establish, plan, protect, and maintain urban forests. Education and awareness campaigns should be intensified concerning urban forestry.

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